

To Assess the Biochemical Parameters in Patients with Psychiatric DisordersVivek Pratap Singh¹, Archana Javadekar², Ekram Goyal³¹Assistant Professor, Department of Psychiatry, Netaji Subhash Medical College & Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India²Professor, Department of Psychiatry, Dr. D. Y. Patil Medical College, Hospital and Research Centre, Pimpri, Pune, Maharashtra, India³Assistant Professor, Department of Psychiatry, B.R. Ambedkar State Institute of Medical Sciences, Punjab, India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Archana Javadekar

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Aim:** The aim of the present study was to assess the biochemical parameters in patients with psychiatric disorders.**Methods:** The cross-sectional study was conducted at Dr. D. Y. Patil Medical College, Hospital and Research Centre, Pimpri, Pune from July 2015 to September 2017 and 126 patients were included in the study.**Results:** The majority of patients 78(61.9%) were in the age group of less than 40 years and there were 48(38.1%) cases who were aged more than 40 years. Majority of cases were females 67(53.2%) and 59(46.8%) cases were males. 56(44.4%) cases were illiterates, 36 patients (28.6%) were educated upto primary level, 14(11.1%) were from higher secondary level, 12(9.5%) were graduates and 8(6.3%) were educated upto secondary level. 71(56.35%) cases were having elevated triglycerides and 55(43.65%) cases were having triglyceride level under normal range. 83(65.9%) patients showed reduced HDL and 43(34.1%) cases were having HDL under normal range. 86(68.25%) were having their LDL under normal range and 40(31.75%) were having elevated LDL. 91(72.22%) cases were having their cholesterol under normal range and 35(27.78%) had increased cholesterol levels. 100(79.37%) cases were normotensive and 26(20.63%) were hypertensive.**Conclusion:** The blood tests to be demanded for vitamin deficiencies are of high importance in terms of early diagnosis, treatment and prognosis. In clinical practice, the diagnosis of psychiatric patients it depends on physician's clinical experiences, clinical symptoms and patient's self-assessments. In the current study, these biochemical parameters are objective and the composite information from these routine biochemical markers may improve the diagnostic effectiveness of depressive disorder.**Keywords:** Biochemical Parameters, Patients, Psychiatric Disorders.

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Introduction

The National Depressive and Manic-Depressive Association investigated the diagnosis and treatment conditions of bipolar disorder (BD) in 2000, and the results indicated that 69% of cases were misdiagnosed. [1] A mean of four psychiatrists were consulted by a patient with BD before receiving the accurate diagnosis, with over one-third taking 10 years before being correctly diagnosed. [1]

The proportion of BD misdiagnosed as major depressive disorder (MDD) in clinical practice was reported as 20.8% nationwide in China. [2] The long-term consistency rate of MDD cases across a 10-year study was only 45.5% [3] compared with 71.9% in a 7-year cohort study of BD cases. [4] The misdiagnosis rate has not substantially

decreased over the past nearly 20 years. Mitochondrial malfunction, inflammatory cytokines, and activated microglia were pointed out as potential biomarkers of BD from the perspective of oxidative stress and neurogenic inflammation. [5-7] The oxidative stress of mood disorders may lead to inflammatory changes in multisystem function, which may be detected by laboratory examination. [8,9] Downstream parameters of inflammatory response are likely to be more available for clinical use in routine blood testing using peripheral blood. [10]

After that thought, we extracted our database and found 14 inflammatory markers of patients with mood disorders having different elevated levels [11], such as uric acid (UA), direct bilirubin

(DBIL), and lactic dehydrogenase (LDH). The data-driven analytics based on inflammation have not yet been proven between BD and MDD. Thus, we speculated that biochemical and endocrine parameters deserve potential development. [12]

Metabolic disorder is a group of heterogeneous disorder characterized by central obesity, dyslipidemia, abnormal glucose tolerance and hypertension. The pathophysiology remains unclear but it has been speculated that development of metabolic syndrome involves insulin resistance and a proinflammatory state. [13,14] The criterions which are widely accepted and provide a differential profile for Asian population are The National Cholesterol Education Programme Adult Treatment Panel (ATPIII) and The International Diabetes Federation. These mainly lay emphasis on abdominal obesity. The other noted criteria are triglyceride level, HDL, systolic blood pressure, diastolic blood pressure and fasting plasma glucose levels. International Diabetes Federation definition requires central obesity plus any other two or more of five criteria whereas the updated ATPIII definition requires any three or more of five criteria. [15-17]

The aim of the present study was to assess the biochemical parameters in patients with psychiatric disorders.

Materials and Methods

The cross-sectional study was conducted at Dr. D. Y. Patil Medical College, Hospital and Research centre, Pimpri, Pune from July 2015 to September 2017 and 126 patients were included in the study.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients presenting with psychiatric disorders at a tertiary care centre for the first time
- Patients taking some psychotropic medications
- Adults >20yrs Old

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients who refused to give consent
- Pregnant women with psychiatric illness
- All those who have delivered a child in past 1 year

Ethics

IEC (Institute ethics committee) clearance was obtained before starting the study.

Written and informed consent was obtained, from all patients.

Methodology:

Informed consent was taken from all the patients who were the part of this study. At any point any patient who was found to be incompetent on the basis of severity of any illness to provide informed

consent the caregiver who were staying with the patient were approached for the same. After explaining the purpose and design of the study all the patients who were diagnosed with psychiatric disorders according to ICD-10 by two senior psychiatrists of tertiary health care system were recruited.

Patient's age, demographic features; family history, level of education, duration of disease, use of alcohol and or nicotine, use of concomitant medications or psychotropic drug history, history of diagnosis and treatment of diabetes, dyslipidaemia, hypertension or any other medical conditions was also evaluated and mentioned. Calibrated Scales was used to measure body weight and height in kilograms and centimeters respectively. Waist circumference was measured at a point taken midway between inferior costal margin and superior iliac crest at the end of normal expiration while standing. Blood pressure in supine position was noted by using standard mercury manometer and at least two readings at five minutes intervals were taken. If blood pressure was >140/90 mm of Hg then a third reading after 30 minutes was recorded and the lowest of these readings was taken. Fasting blood sugar, triglyceride, high density lipoprotein values were also estimated by taking fasting venous samples under aseptic measures. Metabolic Syndrome was diagnosed in the enlisted study group from the data obtained after obtaining all the biochemical values and comparing the values with the base values which were mentioned in the International Diabetes Federation Criteria and then 10 years cardiovascular risk was assessed in the same patient by using the Framingham risk scoring. The data obtained according to the study requirement was analyzed using the proper statistical methods.

Tools

International Diabetes Federation Criteria (IDF): Metabolic syndrome was first defined by International Diabetes Federation in 2006 and of all the criterion which were used this was the only criteria which was epidemiologically and clinically relevant. This was well adapted as these provided a differential profile for Asian populations. These definitions gave priority to abdominal obesity (Abdominal circumference of ≥ 90 cms and ≥ 80 cms for men and women of Asian origin respectively and 102cms and 88cms for Non-Asians male and females respectively. The other criteria used was Triglyceride levels of > 150 mg/dl, a systolic blood pressure ≥ 130 mm of Hg or a diastolic blood pressure ≥ 85 mm of Hg, A fasting plasma glucose level of ≥ 100 mg/dl, high density lipoproteins of < 40 mg/dl and 50 mg/dl for men and women respectively. The IDF criteria need central obesity plus any other two or more out of five criteria. [17]

Framingham Cardiovascular Risk Score (FRS):

The Framingham Risk Score is a sex specific algorithm that was used to estimate the 10 years cardiovascular risk of an individual.

The score was estimated on the basis of age, sex, total cholesterol, high density lipoprotein (HDL) cholesterol, diabetes mellitus, smoking habits and systolic arterial pressure.

The Framingham Risk Score first originated based on the data that was obtained from Framingham Heart Study to estimate the 10 years risk of developing coronary heart disease.

In addition to coronary heart disease prediction 10 years cardiovascular disease risk, periphery artery

disease, heart failure, cerebrovascular events were subsequently added in 2008 Framingham Risk Score. [18]

Statistical Analysis: The scales were scored as per the test manual. Data was collected, compiled and tabulated. The statistical analysis was done using parametric test and the final interpretation was based on Z test (standard normal variate) with 95% level of significance. Results were statistically analyzed using the software: - Statistical package for the social science (SPSS) Version 21. Parametric data was analyzed by paired and unpaired T test. Frequency data was analyzed by chi square test.

Results**Table 1: Baseline characteristics**

Age (Yrs)	No of cases	Percentage
21 – 30	40	31.7
31 – 40	38	30.2
41 – 50	32	25.4
>50	16	12.7
Sex		
Male	59	46.8
Female	67	53.2
Education		
Illiterate	56	44.4
Primary	36	28.6
Secondary	8	6.3
Higher secondary	14	11.1
Graduate	12	9.5
Marital status		
Married	79	62.7
Unmarried	41	32.5
Separated	2	1.6
Divorced	4	3.2
Residence		
Rural	68	54
Urban	58	46
Occupation		
Unskilled	71	56.3
Skilled	23	18.3
Housewife	17	13.5
Student	4	3.2
Unemployed	11	8.7

The majority of patients 78(61.9%) were in the age group of less than 40 years and there were 48(38.1%) cases who were aged more than 40 years. Majority of cases were females 67(53.2%) and 59(46.8%) cases were males. 56(44.4%) cases were illiterates, 36 patients (28.6%) were educated upto primary level,14(11.1%) were from higher secondary level,12(9.5%) were graduates and 8(6.3%) were educated upto secondary level.

79(62.7%) cases were married, 41 cases(32.5%) were unmarried,4(3.2%) were divorced and 2(1.6%) cases were separated. 68(54%) patients were belonging to rural areas and 58(46%) cases were from urban India.

71(56.3%) cases were unskilled, 23(18.3%) were skilled, 17(13.5%) were housewife,11(8.7%) cases were unemployed and 4(3.2%) cases were students.

Table 2: Biochemical parameters

Triglyceride (mg/dl)		
Increased(≥ 150)	71	56.35
Normal(<150)	55	43.65
HDL (mg/dl)		
Reduced	83	65.9
Normal	43	34.1
LDL (mg/dl)		
Increased (≥ 100)	40	31.75
Normal (<100)	86	68.25
Total cholesterol (mg/dl)		
Increased (≥ 200)	35	27.78
Normal (<200)	91	72.22
Blood pressure (mmHg)		
Hypertensive	26	20.63
Normotensive	100	79.37
FBG (mg/dl)		
Increased (≥ 100)	25	19.8
Normal (<100)	101	80.2
BMI		
<18.5	9	7.1
18.5 – 24.99	43	34.1
25 – 29.99	61	48.4
>30	13	10.3
Metabolic syndrome		
Present	47	37.3
Absent	79	62.7

71(56.35%) cases were having elevated triglycerides and 55(43.65%) cases were having triglyceride level under normal range. 83(65.9%) patients showed reduced HDL and 43(34.1%) cases were having HDL under normal range. 86(68.25%) were having their LDL under normal range and 40(31.75%) were having elevated LDL. 91(72.22%) cases were having their cholesterol under normal range and 35(27.78%) had increased cholesterol levels. 100(79.37%) cases were normotensive and 26(20.63%) were hypertensive. 101(80.2%) cases were having their fasting blood glucose under normal range and 25(19.8%) cases were having increased fasting blood glucose. 61(48.4%) cases were overweight, 43(34.1%) cases were normal, 13(10.3%) were obese and 9(7.1%) cases were underweight. 47(37.3%) patients were having metabolic syndrome as compared to 79(62.7%) who were not having metabolic syndrome.

Discussion

Schizophrenia is a psychiatric disorder involving chronic or recurrent psychosis. It is generally related to disorders in social or professional functionality. [19] It is ranked as one of the top ten illnesses that contribute to the global burden of disease and defined as one of the most disabling and economically catastrophic medical disorders by the World Health Organization. [20] Bipolar disorder is a mood disorder characterized with

mania attacks, hypomania, and major depression. [19] When several studies are investigated, schizophrenia and bipolar disorder are seen to be related with certain biochemical parameters. To illustrate, psychosis, behavioral disorder, and depression may accompany hypothyroidism; anxiety, hyperactivity, labile personality, mania, temporary psychosis may rather accompany hyperthyroidism. [21]

The majority of patients 78(61.9%) were in the age group of less than 40 years and there were 48(38.1%) cases who were aged more than 40 years. This finding was consistent with a study done by Lakhan et al [22] which showed that age is an important predictor of mental illness in the population irrespective of the residential settings. Majority of cases were females 67(53.2%) and 59(46.8%) cases were males.

This was in accordance to a study done by Malhotra et al [23] where they found that gender differences occurs in mental disorder but women predominates. 56(44.4%) cases were illiterates, 36 patients (28.6%) were educated upto primary level, 14(11.1%) were from higher secondary level, 12(9.5%) were graduates and 8(6.3%) were educated upto secondary level. This was consistent with a study done by Gomes et al [24] where maximum number of individual suffering from mental disorders had completed their studies only till their secondary education and another possible

explanation would be that poor education can decrease people skills and could lead to faulty coping mechanism making them prone to mental health illnesses. [25] 71(56.35%) cases were having elevated triglycerides and 55(43.65%) cases were having triglyceride level under normal range. 83(65.9%) patients showed reduced HDL and 43(34.1%) cases were having HDL under normal range. 86(68.25%) were having their LDL under normal range and 40(31.75%) were having elevated LDL. 91(72.22%) cases were having their cholesterol under normal range and 35(27.78%) had increased cholesterol levels. 100(79.37%) cases were normotensive and 26(20.63%) were hypertensive. 101(80.2%) cases were having their fasting blood glucose under normal range and 25(19.8%) cases were having increased fasting blood glucose. 61(48.4%) cases were overweight, 43(34.1%) cases were normal, 13(10.3%) were obese and 9(7.1%) cases were underweight. 47(37.3%) patients were having metabolic syndrome as compared to 79(62.7%) who were not having metabolic syndrome. This was in accordance to a study conducted by Mileibys et al [26] where almost 40 percent cases were having altered serum cholesterol, HDL and LDL. In another study by Bradshaw et al [27] it was found that individuals who experiences mental health illnesses were more likely to be obese than others in general population. Several reasons have been proposed for high level of obesity and deranged lab and metabolic parameters which includes shared biological vulnerability between mental health illnesses and abnormal metabolic processes along with unhealthy lifestyles and emerging evidences also support use of psychotropic medicines as a risk factor.

Conclusion

The blood tests to be demanded for vitamin deficiencies are of high importance in terms of early diagnosis, treatment and prognosis. In clinical practice, the diagnosis of psychiatric patients it depends on physician's clinical experiences, clinical symptoms and patient's self-assessments. In the current study, these biochemical parameters are objective and the composite information from these routine biochemical markers may improve the diagnostic effectiveness of depressive disorder.

References

1. Hirschfeld RM, Lewis L, Vornik LA. Perceptions and impact of bipolar disorder: how far have we really come? Results of the national depressive and manic-depressive association 2000 survey of individuals with bipolar disorder. *Journal of Clinical Psychiatry*. 2003 Feb 2; 64(2):161-74.
2. Xiang YT, Zhang L, Wang G, Hu C, Ungvari GS, Dickerson FB, Kilbourne AM, Si TM,

- Fang YR, Lu Z, Yang HC. Sociodemographic and clinical features of bipolar disorder patients misdiagnosed with major depressive disorder in China. *Bipolar disorders*. 2013 Mar; 15(2):199-205.
3. Ruggero CJ, Kotov R, Carlson GA, Tanenberg-Karant M, González DA, Bromet EJ. Diagnostic consistency of major depression with psychosis across 10 years. *The Journal of clinical psychiatry*. 2011 Aug 9; 72(9):4445.
4. Hung YN, Yang SY, Kuo CJ, Lin SK. Diagnostic consistency and interchangeability of schizophrenic disorders and bipolar disorders: A 7-year follow-up study. *Psychiatry and clinical neurosciences*. 2018 Mar; 72(3):180-8.
5. Canales-Rodríguez EJ, Pomarol-Clotet E, Radua J, Sarró S, Alonso-Lana S, Bonnín CD, Goikolea JM, Maristany T, García-Álvarez R, Vieta E, McKenna P. Structural abnormalities in bipolar euthymia: a multicontrast molecular diffusion imaging study. *Biological psychiatry*. 2014 Aug 1; 76(3):239-48.
6. Pinto JV, Passos IC, Librenza-Garcia D, Marcon G, Schneider MA, Conte JH, da Silva J, Lima LP, Quincozes-Santos A, Kauer-Sant'Anna M, Kapczinski F. Neuron-glia interaction as a possible pathophysiological mechanism of bipolar disorder. *Current Neuropharmacology*. 2018 Jun 1; 16(5):519-32.
7. Mechawar N, Savitz J. Neuropathology of mood disorders: do we see the stigmata of inflammation? *Translational psychiatry*. 2016 Nov; 6(11):e946-.
8. Felger JC. Imaging the role of inflammation in mood and anxiety-related disorders. *Current neuropharmacology*. 2018 Jun 1; 16(5):533-58.
9. Pan JX, Xia JJ, Deng FL, Liang WW, Wu J, Yin BM, Dong MX, Chen JJ, Ye F, Wang HY, Zheng P. Diagnosis of major depressive disorder based on changes in multiple plasma neurotransmitters: a targeted metabolomics study. *Translational psychiatry*. 2018 Jul 10; 8(1):130.
10. Wu X, Niu Z, Zhu Y, Shi Y, Qiu H, Gu W, Liu H, Zhao J, Yang L, Wang Y, Liu T. Peripheral biomarkers to predict the diagnosis of bipolar disorder from major depressive disorder in adolescents. *European archives of psychiatry and clinical neuroscience*. 2022 Aug; 272(5):817-26.
11. Zhu Y, Wu X, Liu H, Niu Z, Zhao J, Wang F, Mao R, Guo X, Zhang C, Wang Z, Chen J. Employing biochemical biomarkers for building decision tree models to predict bipolar disorder from major depressive disorder. *Journal of affective disorders*. 2022 Jul 1; 308:190-8.
12. Han Y, Ji H, Liu L, Zhu Y, Jiang X. The relationship of functional status of cortisol, testosterone, and parameters of metabolic syndrome

- in male schizophrenics. *BioMed Research International*. 2020; 2020(1):912-4520.
13. Reaven GM. Role of insulin resistance in human disease (syndrome X): an expanded definition. *Annual review of medicine*. 1993 Feb; 44(1):121-31.
 14. Chambers JC, Eda S, Bassett P, Karim Y, Thompson SG, Gallimore JR, Pepys MB, Kooner JS. C-reactive protein, insulin resistance, central obesity, and coronary heart disease risk in Indian Asians from the United Kingdom compared with European whites. *Circulation*. 2001 Jul 10; 104(2):145-50.
 15. Expert Panel on Detection, Evaluation, and Treatment of High Blood Cholesterol in Adults. Executive Summary of the Third Report of the National Cholesterol Education Program (NCEP) Expert Panel on Detection, Evaluation, and Treatment of High Blood Cholesterol in Adults (Adult Treatment Panel III). *JAMA*. 2001 May 16; 285(19):2486-97.
 16. Grundy SM, Cleeman JI, Daniels SR, Donato KA, Eckel RH, Franklin BA, Gordon DJ, Krauss RM, Savage PJ, Smith Jr SC, Spertus JA. Diagnosis and management of the metabolic syndrome: an American Heart Association/National Heart, Lung, and Blood Institute scientific statement. *Circulation*. 2005 Oct 25; 112(17):2735-52.
 17. Alberti KG, Zimmet P, Shaw J. Metabolic syndrome—a new world-wide definition. A consensus statement from the international diabetes federation. *Diabetic medicine*. 2006 May; 23(5):469-80.
 18. Mahmood, Levy, Vasan, Wang. The Framingham Heart Study and the epidemiology of cardiovascular disease: a historical perspective. *Lancet*. 2013; 383 (9921): 999–1008.
 19. American Psychiatric Association. *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, Fifth Edition (DSM-5)*, American Psychiatric Association, Arlington, VA 2013.
 20. Murray CJL, Lopez AD. *The Global Burden of Disease*, Harvard University Press, Cambridge, MA 1996:21.
 21. Rai V, Yadav U, Kumar P, Yadav SK, Gupta S. Methylenetetra hydro Folate reductase A1298C genetic variant & risk of schizophrenia: A meta-analysis. *Indian J Med Res*. 2017; 145(4):437-47.
 22. Lakhan R, Ekundayò O. National sample survey organization survey report: An estimation of prevalence of mental illness and its association with age in India. *Journal of Neurosciences in Rural Practice*. 2015; 6(1):51.
 23. Malhotra S, Shah R. Women and mental health in India: An overview. *Indian Journal of Psychiatry*. 2015; 57(6):205.
 24. Gomes V, Miguel T, Miasso A. Common Mental Disorders: socio-demographic and pharmacotherapy profile. *Revista Latino-Americana de Enfermagem*. 2013; 21(6):1203-1211.
 25. Manners A, Schnabel L, Hernandez Judy E, Silberg, Eaves. The Relationship between Education and Mental Health: New Evidence from a Discordant Twin Study. *LSoc Forces*. 2016; 95 (1): 107-131
 26. Mileibys S, Mary L, Elevina P, Sara B, Miguel A F, et al. Dyslipidemia Prevalence of Severe Mentally Ill Patients Who are under Pharmacotherapy Scheme. *Food Sci & Nutri Tech* 2016; 1(1): FSNT-MS-ID-000101.
 27. Bradshaw T, Mairs H. Obesity and Serious Mental Ill Health: A Critical Review of the Literature. *Healthcare*. 2014; 2(2):166-182.